

D6.3 (M48) - Reports on the implementation of resources (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

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Context

ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR, has engaged in the harmonisation of computational solutions for life science. This report, Deliverable 6.3, concerns the workflows, tools, and databases implemented for the processing of biodiversity data and datasets by Work Package 6 (WP6). This deliverable focuses on enhancing reproducibility and scalability in genomic annotation processes through the development of modular and automated workflows. These efforts aim to align with best practices in computational genomics while addressing the specific needs of biodiversity data analysis.

Delivery

- The `lrsday_lite` project represents a streamlined implementation of the Long-read sequencing data analysis for yeasts (LRSDAY) annotation workflow (Yue, J. X., & Liti, G. 2018), specifically designed to exclude the assembly stage while maintaining high reproducibility and automation. This implementation leverages the Snakemake workflow management system to convert traditional shell scripts into modular Snakemake rules, thereby improving transparency and scalability in genomic annotation processes.
- The workflow is delivered as a Snakemake-based pipeline with integrated dependency management through Conda environments. While most tools are installed via Conda, certain components—including RepeatMasker libraries—are downloaded and configured externally during the setup phase.

- The annotation pipeline requires the input assembly to be placed.
- The workflow is published on GitHub: https://github.com/mdondrup/lrsday_lite

Outcomes

- The lrsday_lite is licensed under the MIT License and the workflow provides a reproducible and modular framework for genome annotation, aligning with best practices in computational genomics.

References

Yue, J. X., & Liti, G. (2018). Long-read sequencing data analysis for yeasts. *Nature protocols*, 13(6), 1213–1231. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2018.025>